

THE ACOUSTIC AND IMPACT RESPONSE OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES BASED ON NATURAL FIBER REINFORCED SKINS AND Balsa WOOD

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich structure with plant fiber skins and balsawood core is a type of new green composites which might yield a multifunctional structure. In this study, two types of core materials (balsa wood and PET foam) were applied to fabricate sandwich structures with flax fiber reinforced epoxy skins. Besides, the corresponding sandwich structures with glass fiber reinforced skins were also prepared for comparison. The sound absorption coefficients of two types of core and their sandwich composites were measured by the two-microphone transfer function technique in the impedance tube. Moreover, a number of tests were then performed on balsa wood core sandwich panels under various impact energies. Damage process of the sandwich composites was analyzed from cross-examining load-deflection curves, energy profile diagrams and the damaged specimens. The damage process of sandwich based on PET foam were also investigated for comparison. It was concluded that this green sandwich structure had a superior sound absorption property and competitive energy absorption property compare to synthetic sandwich structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The uses of natural fibers and their products in applications of eco-friendly products raised more and more attentions in recent years [1]. Plant fibers are extracted from plant stems and leaves and other parts, with the advantage for rich source, low price, specific strength, high specific modulus and so on. Plant fibers have complex multi-scaled hollow structure compared with synthetic fibers [2], as shown in Figure 1. The unique microstructures bring more advantages for plant fiber reinforced composite materials compares to the solid synthetic fibers, such as sound absorbing [3-5] or energy absorption [6] and heat insulation properties [7,8] and so on.

Cellular materials with high volume of pores have been greatly regarded as an effective noise absorption material due to their effective sound damping, low density etc. Balsa wood can be considered as a kind of cellular materials, it is composed of fibers, rays and vessels, there are also many micro pores connect each grain, as shown in Figure 2. This structure lowers the density and make it has the potential of being sound absorbing materials. The long prismatic grain of balsa resembling a hexagon in the transvers cross section. Gibson and Ashby [9] found certain woods as a kind of cellular solids have acoustic properties make them specially attractive for the sound boards of musical instruments. Balsa is one of the fastest growing and lightest wood species with density ranges from 100 to 250 kg/m³. The low density is extremely valuable in applications that require lightweight materials with good mechanical performance. Balsa wood is considered as one of the preferred core

materials in structural sandwich panels for wind turbine blades, sporting equipment, boats and aircraft [10].

Figure. 1 The microstructure of a single flax fiber.

Figure 2 The microstructures of (a) transverse section of balsa wood. (b) longitudinal section of balsa wood.

Utilizing natural materials as face sheets or core materials for sandwich structures would provide superior load bearing and fatigue properties, and are preferred in many applications with weight constraints such as aerospace, wind turbine blades and automobiles [11]. This kind of sandwich structures have potentials of being employed in transportation and construction fields. Therefore, it is important to ascertain their sound absorption performance and deformation along with fracture behavior under both static and dynamic loadings.

In this work, the sound absorption performance of sandwich structure based on flax fiber reinforced skins and balsa core was evaluated using the impedance tube method. With a purpose of comparison, commonly used traditional sandwich composites with glass fiber face sheets and PET foam core were also investigated. Acoustic properties are often a secondary design criteria in sandwich structures, the mechanical performance and weight are primary concerns. Therefore, the impact performance of these sandwich structure were also evaluated through low-velocity impact test.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

Unidirectional flax fabrics were used to reinforce with epoxy as skins and balsa wood as the core materials to fabricate Flax-Balsa sandwich structures. Likewise, Flax-PET and Glass-PET sandwich structures were prepared for comparison. The NPEL-128 epoxy was supplied by Shanghai Zhongsi Industry Co. Ltd, China. The unidirectional flax fabric was provided by Lineo Co. Ltd, Belgium and the unidirectional glass fabric was provided by Zhejiang Mengtai Reinforced Composite Material Co. Ltd. The balsa wood and the AIREX® T92.100 PET foam were supplied by Zhuhai Dechi Technology Co. Ltd and 3A Composites (China) Ltd, respectively. The detail parameters of the flax and glass fiber fabric materials used for fabricating the sandwich structures skins were listed in Table 1. Balsa wood and PET foam with thickness of 10 mm were prepared as core materials to fabricate sandwich structure. The basic

parameters of these two types of core materials were shown in Table 2. Balsa wood and AIREX® T92.100 PET foam with similar density and porosity were selected in this study for comparison.

Table 1 The details of fiber fabrics used in manufacturing sandwich structures skins.

Materials	Areal density (g/m ²)	Thickness (mm)	Specific Strength (MPa/g/cm ³)	Specific Modulus (GPa/g/cm ³)
Unidirectional flax fabric	213.3	0.2	1034	55
Unidirectional glass fabric	207.5	0.1	980	30

Table 2 The parameters of core materials used to manufacturing sandwich structures

Materials	Average Density (kg/m ³)	Porosity	Average Cellular Diameter (μm)	Axial Compression Modulus (MPa)	Transverse Compression Modulus (MPa)
Balsa wood (longitudinal direction)	125	0.92	35-40	280-320	30-80
PET foam	112	0.933	500-700	90	90

2.2 Sandwich structures fabrication

The epoxy resin, curing agent and accelerating agent were mixed at the weight ratio of 100:80:1. The unidirectional flax and glass fabrics were impregnated with the resin system, then the impregnated fabrics were laid on the top and bottom surfaces of core materials according to the stacking sequences listed in Table 3. Then the prepreg and core materials were placed in a hot press machine under pressure of 1 MPa and temperature of 120° C for 2 hours in order to be completely cured. Three kinds of sandwich structures were prepared. Flax-Balsa and Flax-PET denote the sandwich structures based on flax fiber reinforced skins and balsa or PET foam cores, respectively. The Glass-PET denotes sandwich structure with glass fiber reinforced skins and PET foam core. The details of the resulting sandwich structures were given in Table 3.

Table 3 The details of three types of the sandwich structures.

Sandwich Structures	Skin Thickness (mm)	Core Thickness (mm)	Stacking Sequence of Skins	Fiber Volume Content of Skins	Porosity of Core
Flax-Balsa	2.1	10	[0/90/0] _s	48%	0.920
Flax-PET	2.1	10	[0/90/0] _s	48%	0.933
Glass-PET	2.1	10	[0 ₂ /90 ₂ /0 ₂] _s	48%	0.933

2.3 Acoustic property measurement

The Sound Absorption Coefficient (SAC) of sandwich composites was measured through a transfer function technique with the impedance tube facilities manufactured by BSWA Technology Co. Ltd. The SAC is defined as the ratio of the absorbed sound energy and the incident sound energy. The measurements were conducted according to ISO10534-2 standard at frequencies from 400 Hz to 6300 Hz at 25°C and 60% relative humidity, and at least three specimens were tested for each group. The measurements are composed of SW422, SW477 impedance tubes with diameters of 100 and 30 for measuring frequencies from 400–2000 and 800–6300 Hz, respectively.

2.4 Low-velocity impact test

The impact tests were performed on 10×10 cm² square sandwich structures using an instrumented drop weight testing system INSTRON CEAST 9350. The total mass of the dropping weight was 5.277 kg with a hemispherical nose of 16 mm attached to the impact mass. The specimens were clamped with 200 N force using a pneumatic fixture with a 76 mm diameter inside hole, for the boundary condition of the axisymmetric solid support. The impact energies ranged from 2 to 25 Joules.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 The Sound Absorption Response of Sandwich Structures

Figure 3 illustrates the variation of sound absorption coefficient with frequency of Flax-Balsa and Flax-PET sandwich structures and their corresponding core materials. It can be seen that the SACs increase with test frequency for all the samples. For sandwich structures, the sound absorption coefficients are higher than that of the core materials in all frequency levels, especially for Flax-Balsa sandwich structure at frequency from 1600 to 6300 Hz. When sound wave transmit from one material to another material, part of the sound energy will be reflected. The sound wave in sandwich structure will reflect frequently between two composite skins and dissipated efficiently due to its multi-layer structure. Moreover, it was found that the SAC value gap between sandwich structures and core materials get bigger as the frequency increases. It is because that as the increase of the frequency of the sound wave, the vibration and dissipation increase and the sandwich structure can absorb more sound energy than the individual core material. It is obviously that the special multilayer structure of sandwich has good effect on the sound absorption property at a large range of frequency band.

Figure 3 SACs of sandwich structures and their corresponding core materials.

The SACs of sandwich structures fabricated with PET core and different skins are shown in Figure 4. It can be observed that the sandwich structure with the flax fiber fabric reinforced skins has a higher sound absorption coefficient and this gap is much larger at high frequency. Here, flow resistance is defined as the resistance of the material to airflow and can be expressed by equation (1).

$$\sigma = \frac{\Delta p}{d \cdot v} \quad (1)$$

where σ is the flow resistance, v is the particle velocity through material, Δp is sound pressure differential across the material and d is the thickness of the buck. When the yarns are non-overlapped, the flow resistance can be predicted by equation (2) [12].

$$\sigma = 108.8 \frac{\eta}{d^2} \quad (2)$$

where d is the diameter of yarns, η is the dynamic viscosity of the air and equals to $1.84 \times 10^{-5} Pa \cdot s$. The fibers' diameter of flax is much larger than that of glass fiber, as shown in Table 4, which leads to a smaller flow resistance of flax fabrics. The larger fiber diameter and smaller flow resistance of the plant fiber make it easier for sound energy to enter the interior of the sandwich structure for dissipation.

Figure 4 SACs of sandwich structures with different skins.

Table 4 Flow resistance of glass fabrics and flax fabrics.

	Diameter of fibers (μm)	Flow resistance(Nm^{-4}s)
Flax fabrics	25	8.9×10^5
Glass fabrics	11	2.4×10^6

Figure 5 illustrates the SACs of sandwich structures with flax fiber reinforced skins but with different cores. It can be observed that the Flax-Balsa sandwich structure possess a higher sound absorption coefficient than that of Flax-PET sandwich structure in the frequency band of 1600 to 6300 Hz. However, the one with PET core showed a better low frequency sound absorption performance, at 400-1600 Hz. It can be observed from the microstructures of balsa and PET from Figure 6 that the average diameter of cells of balsa is much smaller than that of the PET foam. By measuring, the average diameter of cells in balsa is 35-40 μm , which in PET foam is 500-700 μm . In the process of sound propagation, sound energy will be converted into heat with the effect of heat exchange and viscous resistance. The smaller cellular diameter of balsa means more cells within the same volume, which is conducive to improve the sound absorption properties.

It also can be seen that balsa is composed of vertical array of cells, exhibiting a honeycomb-like appearance in the transverse section. The pores can be connected to the wood interior through the interconnected cell cavity consequently. The acoustic wave is a longitudinal wave, which propagating direction is in the same direction with the axial parenchyma fibers of balsa. Therefore, in the process of sound wave propagation, a large amount of gaps interconnected with the internal space make more sound waves propagate inside the wood and can be absorbed, improving the sound absorption properties. However, the cells in PET foam shaped in ball or ellipse, the gaps in cells can hardly extend into the interior of the material. It makes sound wave more difficult to get inside the material for dissipation. Generally, the differences in microstructure of balsa and PET foam make balsa has a better sound absorption property.

The loss of sound energy is mainly due to the contribution of porous sound absorption mechanism and resonance absorption mechanism. The contribution of the resonance absorption is

related to the thickness of cell wall, the shape of cells, the component of the core material and so on. Accordingly, a different effect was present in the frequency below 1600 Hz, despite the balsa core has a better overall sound absorption performance.

Figure 5 SACs of flax reinforced sandwich structures with different cores.

Figure 6 Microstructures of (a) Balsa wood and (b) PET foam.

3.2 The Impact Energy Absorption Response of Sandwich Structures

Figure 7 illustrated impact load-deflection curves of three different sandwiches. It can be seen from the curves that for all impact energy, the curve slope of the ascending segment of Flax-Balsa sandwich structures, namely bending modulus, is larger than that of Glass-PET and Flax-PET sandwich structure, leading to the greater impact force and smaller displacement of balsa wood sandwich structures compare to Flax-PET sandwich panel. However, Glass-PET sandwich panel has the highest impact peak load for the same impact energy, due to the higher stiffness of glass fiber compare to the flax fiber. The energy absorption of Flax-Balsa was higher than that of Glass-Balsa and Flax-PET sandwich panels. The Flax-PET sandwich structures has the largest deformation. Moreover, the damage areas of balsa wood based sandwich panels were smaller than for the PET based sandwiches.

Figure 7 The impact load-deformation of three sandwich structures following impact energy of (a) 2 Joules, (b) 5 Joules, (c) 10 Joules and (d) 25 Joules.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Environmental friendly sandwich structure with flax fiber reinforced skins and balsa wood core was fabricated. Due to the low flow resistance and characteristic impedance of plant fiber reinforced skins and the unique porous structure of the balsa core, the Flax-Balsa sandwich structure possessed good sound absorption properties compared to sandwich structure based on PET foam core. The sound absorption properties of Flax-Balsa sandwich panel was affected by the density of the balsa wood core. In addition to the sound absorption performance, Flax-Balsa sandwich structure also has superior impact energy absorption capacity. Therefore, it has the potential to replace synthetic sandwich structures in applications aspects of load-bearing and sound absorption structures.

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